

Neuro-Affirming Speech Therapy Session Checklist

Co-Regulation

- Did I inform the student of who I am and where they are going?
- Did I model the student's preferred co-regulation strategy (e.g., deep breathing, movement)?
- Did I offer environmental choices (e.g., lights on or off)?
- Did I offer and encourage the student to advocate for breaks?
- If the student appeared distressed, did I reduce communication demands?

Student Choice

- Did I offer the student meaningful choice (e.g., activity from a field of three, order of tasks)?
- Did I take an interest in the student's interests?

Communication Access

- Did I model and honor various communication modes (e.g., device, sign language), especially the mode the student prefers?
- Did I ask to touch the student's device before modeling on it?
- Was the device accessible at all times?
- Did I give the student sufficient time to respond?